

Research Article

The Effects of Digital Technologies on Global Citizenship Education in Higher Education

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Abstract: Global Citizenship Education (GCED) is a popular educational initiative that aims to instil in students the knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed to effectively engage in an interconnected world. GCED challenges conventional educational paradigms by emphasizing understanding, empathy, and accountability for global issues such as human rights, social justice, sustainability, and cultural diversity. Global citizenship education has taken on new dimensions and challenges in the digital age, with technology helping to increase its effectiveness and relevance. Digital technologies in global citizenship education, particularly in higher education, should be highlighted to ensure the effectiveness and quality of teaching and learning. The study introduced the concept of global citizenship education in the digital age and reviewed prior research on using digital technologies in global citizenship education. This review consisted of (1) the studies that introduced the concept of global citizenship education or its elements to higher education, (2) the studies that determined the use of digital technologies in global citizenship education, and (3) the studies that investigated the benefits and challenges of digital technologies in global citizenship education. The studies in each group were briefly reviewed. This study made several suggestions and recommendations for higher education's utilization of digital technologies to promote global citizenship education.

Keywords: Digital Technologies; Global Citizenship Education; Higher Education.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Global Citizenship Education (GCED) is an educational approach to develop in learners the knowledge, skills and values to engage together in building a better world for the future (Akkari & Maleq, 2020; UNESCO, 2015). In this study, a brief overview of the Educational Framework for Global Citizenship in Higher Education by Bahadur (2021) sets the stage to explain how global citizenship education transcends traditional educational boundaries because it fosters understanding, empathy and responsibility towards human rights, social justice, sustainability and cultural diversity—global issues that are beyond local contexts. This revival gave rise to a diversity of GCED theoretical perspectives that can be positioned along a spectrum that ranges from the predominantly economic neoliberal at one end to more humanistically and ethically oriented transformative, value-creating, ethical, and critical approaches (Bamber et al., 2018; Bosio & Guajardo, 2024; Bosio & Gregorutti, 2023; Bosio & Waghid, 2023; Papastephanou, 2023).

Global citizenship education has new dimensions and challenges in the digital age, with technology contributing to its effectiveness and relevance. GCED has been conceptualised as an educational response to globalisation and its associated challenges, anchored in specific cosmopolitan

values that emphasise connectedness, cultural sensitivity and concern for others along with skills related to critical thinking and civic engagement (Goren & Yemini, 2017; Mannion et al., 2011). According to Clifford & Montgomery (2017), internationalisation policies in higher education aim to equip graduates with the global citizenship skills. From the frames-of-references of GCED, students will be forged as responsible and conscientious global citizens equipped with the skills for a better world. If these global citizens in-the-making can be reached through the curricula that schools are able to integrate GCED, they will contribute with their learning to themselves and the world community (Bulut et al., 2013; Swarts, 2020). Since ICTs play a fundamental role in GCED, a global citizen is also a digital citizen (Caballero, 2023).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The purpose of this study is to overview current research regarding digital technologies in global citizenship education in higher education. There is a research question that has been selected to guide this research and to ensure that a substantial range of literature was captured relating to the topic of interest:

1. What are the concepts of global citizenship education or its elements in higher education?
2. What are the uses of digital technologies in global citizenship education?
3. What are the benefits and challenges of digital technologies in global citizenship education?

Key concepts and search terms related to digital technologies, global citizenship, higher education was used to capture literature. Inclusion and exclusion criteria have been explained in Table 1.

Table 1. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Criterion	Inclusion	Exclusion
Articles' time	2018-2024	The studies before these dates
Type of reading materials	Journals, books, and educational articles	Articles from websites, newspapers, magazines
Language	English	Non-English studies
Focus of study	Previous studies related to global citizenship, digital technologies, higher education	Articles that are no fulfill the key concepts in the study
Population	Higher educational institutions which have been implemented global citizenship education	Primary and secondary school

Some electronic databases were used to search for articles about the effects of digital technologies on global citizenship education in higher education, including EBSCOhost, Taylor & Francis Online, ProQuest, ScienceDirect, Wiley Online Library, and other valuable online resources. Google Scholar and ResearchGate were used to search for related articles in this study. The collected journals and articles were chosen based on their relevance to this research. As a result, the collected journals are only relevant to global citizenship in higher education; articles on global citizenship in primary or secondary school settings have been excluded. In this study, only full-text articles about

global citizenship were selected during the search process. There are many articles have been removed as the articles are duplicated in the databases. Many articles have been removed due to duplication in the databases. Some articles were found in the chosen databases and on Google Scholar, but they did not meet the inclusion criteria. The primary findings from the collected journals and articles indicate that the effects of digital technologies on global citizenship education are significant in higher education settings.

3. FINDINGS

This review consisted of (1) studies that introduced the concept of global citizenship education or its elements to higher education, (2) studies that determined the use of digital technologies in global citizenship education, and (3) studies that investigated the benefits and challenges of digital technologies in global citizenship education. The studies in each group were briefly reviewed.

3.1 The Concept of Global Citizenship Education or Its Elements to Higher Education

Global citizenship education has been recognized by its importance and values in teaching and learning. The study of Horey et al. (2018) explained the guidelines and relevant information to assist higher education educators and researchers to create clear curricula and evaluate the effectiveness of global citizenship education. Global citizenship is a key factor in preparing students for the global workforce. Higher educational institutions have adopted global citizenship education to encourage students to consider their own and others' roles in local and global contexts (Massaro, 2022). According to Bosio (2022), educators in higher education believe that the GCED should stimulate culturally relevant experiences, promote students' fundamental knowledge of society, and develop students' personal competence. In recent year, GCED can be discussed and separated into 3 research approaches intercultural competence, social identification with a global community, and civic engagement which can guide the readers to understand in detail (Gaitán-Aguilar et al. 2024).

3.2 The Use of Digital Technologies in Global Citizenship Education

The implementation of digital technologies is crucial in teaching and learning. This statement has been supported by the study of Selwyn (2023) that the effectiveness of digital technologies in online learning which can foster the global citizenship education. White (2020) asserted that digital technology is a tool, and how it is used, by whom, and for what reason will determine how it affects global citizenship education (GCED). According to Bosio (2024), a critical pedagogical framework for GCED has been proposed to assist students in online teaching and learning in Japanese Higher Education Institutions. Furthermore, Helm et al. (2024) stated that the utilisation of digital technologies provides opportunities for higher education institutions to involve students in online transnational and global learning experiences, which can help foster a reimagining of educational institutions and society.

3.3 The Benefits and Challenges of Digital Technologies in Global Citizenship Education

Digital transformation education becomes the trend and hot issue after the Covid-19 Pandemic. The transformation of digital technologies and educational innovations can provide opportunities and risks to the education. In other word, the use of technologies can assist the teaching and learning especially in the virtual environment, but there are still some challenges that need to be discussed. According to Pedro et al. (2019), the digital technology such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) can provide positive outcomes as well as challenges in the students' teaching and learning processes. Globalisation necessitated an educational response to prepare young people for productive participation in the emerging global community. Technology could have a positive impact on effective GCED (White,

2020). Furthermore, GCED is crucial in digital age as it helps students navigate the complex information flow, understand their rights online, and engage with others in a responsible and ethical way, education must give them the chance to develop their digital, media, and information literacy skills. It is the responsibilities of educators to make sure that ICTs are used in the classroom and beyond in a way that protects speech freedom, human rights, and information access for all students (UNESCO, 2024).

4. DISCUSSION

This review consisted of (1) studies that introduced the concept of global citizenship education or its elements to higher education, and (2) studies that determined the use of digital technologies in global citizenship education, and (3) studies that investigated the benefits and challenges of digital technologies in global citizenship education. Previous studies showed that global citizenship education is essential to produce the students with relevant knowledge and skills in global collaboration and action (Bosio, 2022; Gaitán-Aguilar et al., 2024; Horey et al., 2018; Massoro, 2022). In the findings above, the use of digital technologies and other educational innovations should be supported by promoting global citizenship education in higher education (Bosio, 2024; Helm et al., 2024; Selwyn, 2023; White, 2020). Besides that, the findings also showed that the use of digital technologies can have their own opportunities and challenges that need to be aware and think wisely before implemented in the teaching and learning (Pedro et al., 2019; UNESCO, 2024).

There are numerous limitations that can be addressed in this review. Due to this review focusses on the higher education context, future research may include both primary and secondary studies. There has been limited study on digital technologies in global citizenship education in Malaysia, despite their importance in improving students' learning and knowledge. The concept of digital citizenship education has emerged as a novel aspect of global citizenship that can be researched and studied.

5. CONCLUSION

This review can serve as a resource for policymakers and lecturers in higher education institutions looking to improve their learning practices in global citizenship education, as well as guidelines for making the learning environment more meaningful to students. The study's findings have commercialization potential in some ways. Policymakers and educators can rethink, plan, and develop relevant digital technologies to improve the effectiveness of global citizenship by focusing on its opportunities and challenges. Global citizenship education has received a lot of attention in recent years and has emerged as an educational trend that can benefit society and the global community.

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